

Regulatory research priorities for AI use in the medicine lifecycle: a European perspective with global relevance

Luis C Pinheiro¹, Amanda C Langston¹, Marie Orre^{1,2}, Joerg Zinserling^{1,3}, Konstantina Boumaki^{1,4}, Bastian VH Hornung^{1,5,6}, Siobhan O'Sullivan^{1,7}, Gabriel Westman^{1,8}, Karl Broich^{1,3}, Peter Arlett^{1,9}

¹ European Medicines Agency, Amsterdam, The Netherlands

² The Dental and Pharmaceutical Benefits Agency, Stockholm, Sweden

³ Federal Institute for Drugs and Medical Devices, Bonn, Germany

⁴ European Patients' Forum, Brussels, Belgium

⁵ Medicines Evaluation Board, Utrecht, The Netherlands

⁶ Julius Center for Health Sciences and Primary Care, University Medical Centre Utrecht, Utrecht, The Netherlands

⁷ Royal College of Surgeons of Ireland, Dublin, Ireland

⁸ Swedish Medical Products Agency, Uppsala, Sweden

⁹ London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine, London, United Kingdom

Corresponding author:

Luis Correia Pinheiro

European Medicines Agency

Domenico Scarlattilaan 6

1083 HS Amsterdam

The Netherlands

+31 (0)88 781 6000

Luis.pinheiro@ema.europa.eu

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Abstract

Regulatory bodies play a central role in providing guidance that enables safe and effective use of artificial intelligence tools in medicine development and evaluation. Regulators can also act as catalysts for regulatory science research. To inform these efforts, a European-wide survey was conducted to solicit stakeholder perspectives on the priority areas for regulatory science research related to the use of artificial intelligence in the medicine lifecycle. Twenty-eight regulatory science research questions were developed covering seven thematic domains: (1) research integrity and intellectual property; (2) accuracy and reliability of AI tools; (3) data governance, confidentiality, and consent; (4) regulation and oversight; (5) ethics, fairness, and bias prevention; (6) resources and support for AI use; and (7) impact on jobs and skills. Within each domain, stakeholders ranked four research challenges. A total of 273 responses were collected from regulators, pharmaceutical industry professionals, patients and consumers, academics, and healthcare professionals. Rankings of research challenges frequently converged across stakeholder groups and levels of AI experience. The top-ranked research questions within each domain were weighted according to the overall importance ranking of each domain to identify a list of ten priority areas of research. The majority of the ten priority areas fell within the domains of “Accuracy & reliability of AI tools,” “Data governance, confidentiality, & consent,” and “Ethics, fairness, & bias prevention.” This list aims to support researchers and research funding bodies in addressing knowledge gaps on artificial intelligence in the medicines lifecycle.

1. Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) tools are increasingly being integrated into the medicine development lifecycle.(1,2) The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development defines an AI system as “a machine-based system that, for explicit or implicit objectives, infers, from the input it receives, how to generate outputs such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that can influence physical or virtual environments. Different AI systems vary in their levels of autonomy and adaptiveness after deployment.”(3) AI tools can support more timely and efficient drug discovery through improved development and evaluation processes.(2,4,5) However, the pharmaceutical industry and regulatory authorities face a diverse range of challenges in implementing these newer tools into medicine development and evaluation.(1,6,7) Data privacy, robust training datasets, lack of interpretability, hallucination risks, and different regulatory standards represent a small sample of commonly-cited challenges in advancing AI adoption within clinical development.(6,8)

Regulatory bodies like the European Medicines Agency (EMA) and National Competent Authorities (NCAs) are tasked with developing guidance that facilitates the deployment of safe and effective use of AI in medicine development and evaluation.(6,9,10) To better understand and address emerging knowledge gaps in this part of the AI use landscape, the Network Data Steering Group (NDSG) from the European Medicines Regulatory Network (EMRN) conducted a European-wide survey. The survey targeted regulators, pharmaceutical industry professionals, patients and consumers, academics, and healthcare professionals.

The primary aim of the survey was to gather stakeholder perspectives on the priority research areas related to the use of AI in the medicine lifecycle, from development to post-authorisation monitoring and evaluation.

To our knowledge, previous studies on utilisation of AI in medicine development have not explored the priority areas of regulatory research as identified by patients, pharmaceutical industries, researchers and regulators. This study aimed to respond to this gap by presenting respondents with pre-defined thematic domains and research challenges to understand which areas were perceived to be the most important. In

addition to exploring priorities by stakeholder group, we examined how priority research areas varied according to participants' self-reported level of AI familiarity.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study design

A cross-sectional survey was developed to capture perspectives from various stakeholder groups on research priorities for the use of AI across the medicines lifecycle. The survey targeted a broad range of stakeholders, including regulatory agencies, pharmaceutical industries, small and medium-sized enterprises, patients, consumers, academics, contract research organisations, and healthcare professionals.

The survey content was informed by a scoping review of existing literature discussing AI implementation in healthcare and medicine, including articles soliciting perspectives from researchers, patients, healthcare professionals, and industry.(11–15)

Based on this review, seven thematic domains were identified to structure the framework of the survey (see table 1), and four specific research questions were developed to reflect potential priority areas for future research within each respective domain (see appendix A).

Table 1: Survey domains and definitions

Domain name	Definition
Research integrity & intellectual property	Responsible conduct of AI-enabled research, with appropriate attribution of contributions and proprietary rights management for data, models, and outputs.
Accuracy & reliability of AI tools	Performance characteristics, explainable outputs, transparent validation practices, and robustness.
Data governance, confidentiality, & consent	Secure, lawful, and ethical handling of patient and user data, including consent and privacy protections.

Regulation & oversight	Accountability and liability frameworks, best practices and guidance, and applicability of current laws and rules to AI tools.
Ethics, fairness, & bias prevention	Ethical development and deployment that avoids bias and discrimination against a group of people and promotes equity.
Resources & support for AI use	People, funding, infrastructure, environmental impact, and tools required for safe, effective, and compliant AI adoption.
Impact on jobs & skills	How AI reshapes roles, demands for skills, and workforce transitions.

To ensure relevance to the European regulatory context, a survey drafting group comprised EMA staff and experts from the EMRN with AI expertise, reviewed and refined the proposed domains. For each domain, four specific research questions were developed to reflect potential priority areas for future research.

The draft survey was peer-reviewed by eleven EMA and EMRN experts in statistics, methodology and AI. They assessed approach, content, completeness, and time to complete. Following this, the survey was piloted amongst volunteer patient representatives, AI experts from NCAs, NDSG members, and academic contributors for usability and readability.

2.2 Data collected

The survey questionnaire was divided into two sections. The first section collected relevant stakeholder information, including stakeholder affiliation, area of work (human, veterinary, or both), years of experience, organisation size, level of AI expertise, and membership in various regulatory groups.

The second section focused on stakeholder opinions across the seven domains, listed in table 1. A Likert scale was used to assess the perceived importance of each domain. Respondents ranked four pre-

specified research questions within each of the seven domains based on their perception of the relative importance of each question. This process was used to identify prioritised questions within each domain. To mitigate clustering of responses at the upper end of the scale, the four associated research questions within each domain were presented in a randomised order and as a forced choice ranking task. The full list of research questions is available in supplementary material A.

Participants were also asked to select three domains that they believe should be prioritised in AI regulatory science studies and to suggest any missing topics or additional comments, allowing for open-ended feedback and identification of potential gaps in the survey scope. A selection of open-ended responses is provided in supplementary material B. The selection of quotes was based on representativeness of overall responses, diversity of stakeholder perspectives, and relevance to the thematic domain.

2.3 Analysis

Descriptive analyses were performed using R (version 4.4.2). For each domain, mean ranking scores were calculated for each research question within its respective domain, with 1 representing the highest possible ranking and 4 representing the lowest possible ranking. Within each domain, the research question with the lowest mean ranking was assigned first overall priority, followed sequentially by questions with higher mean rankings.

The results presented for each domain include three elements: (1) a diverging bar chart to display the average question rankings across all respondents, (2) a subway plot depicting the question rankings by stakeholder group, and (3) a subway plot displaying the question rankings according to each respondents' AI experience level.

The final list of priorities was derived using a structured weighting algorithm to determine which research questions were most prioritised when adjusted by overall domain importance. Rankings within each domain were first inverted (highest-ranked questions assigned a value of 4; lowest-ranked assigned a value of 1). Each domain was then weighted according to the proportion of respondents who identified it as a priority under constrained resources. Question scores were calculated by multiplying the inverted

ranking value by the domain weight, producing a weighted score for every question. No ties occurred. Final priorities were selected by choosing the highest-scoring questions while ensuring proportional representation across domains, such that higher-priority domains contributed more questions and lower-priority domains contributed fewer or none.

3. Results

3.1. Respondent profiles

The survey was conducted using EUSurvey (16) between 29 September and 17 October 2025.

The survey collected 273 responses from stakeholders. Table 2 shows that NCA employees (n=65, 24%) and industry professionals, (n=61, 22%) accounted for a greatest proportion of respondents, while academia and researchers (n=9, 3%), CRO professionals (n=13, 5%), and EU agency professionals (n=9, 3%) represented smaller proportions. Self-reported level of familiarity with AI tools showed that most respondents across all stakeholder groups had some professional experience with AI. As shown in table 2, only four individuals (1%) reported having no prior experience or knowledge of AI, and 42 (15%) have heard of AI but had not used it in a professional context. Many individuals (n=99, 36%) reported having a basic understanding of AI and having used it in a professional context, and 67 respondents (25%) reported active professional use of AI. Thirty respondents (11%) are actively responsible for evaluating or shaping policies on the professional use of AI, while 31 respondents (11%) actively design or develop AI tools professionally. Most professional respondents had substantial experience in their fields, with 43% (n=94) reporting over 15 years of professional engagement and 19% (n=42) reporting over 8 years of professional experience, respectively.

Table 2: Stakeholder group and level of AI experience (N=273)

Category	Sub-category	n (%)
<i>Stakeholder group</i>		
	National competent authority	65 (24%)
	Pharmaceutical industry	61 (22%)

Patients or consumers	40 (15%)
Small and medium-sized enterprises	36 (13%)
Healthcare professionals	26 (10%)
Contract research organisations	13 (5%)
Academia and researchers	9 (3%)
EU agency	9 (3%)
Other	14 (5%)

Level of AI experience

I actively design or develop AI technologies in a professional setting	31 (11%)
I am actively responsible for evaluating or shaping policies on the use of AI technology in a professional setting	30 (11%)
I actively use AI technologies in a professional setting	67 (25%)
I have a basic understanding of AI concepts and have used or studied it in a professional context	99 (36%)
I have heard of AI but have not used or studied it in a professional setting	42 (15%)
I have no prior experience or knowledge of AI	4 (1%)

3.2 Overall prioritisation of research domains

Several respondents indicated in the free-text comments that all seven research domains were highly important. Additionally, the respondents were asked to prioritise three domains to allow us to identify the

overall prioritisation of domains. Overall, *Accuracy and reliability of AI tools* was most often prioritised, and *Resources & support for AI use* and *Impact on jobs & skills* were prioritised least often (figure 1).

Figure 1: Overall prioritisation of research domains (n=273).

Respondents were asked to prioritise three of the seven domains. Bar graph showing the frequency with which each of the seven research domains was selected among respondents' top three priorities in case of limited resources.

3.3. Ranking of research questions

The following domain results are listed in the order of overall prioritisation with the highest priority domain being presented first.

The most prioritised domain in the overall analysis was *Accuracy and reliability of AI tools*, as depicted in figure 1. Figure 2 shows the rankings of the four research questions within this domain. The question *How can the accuracy and reliability of AI models be ensured when generating evidence and informing decisions and how can limits be identified?* was ranked highest by the largest proportion of respondents (n=123, 45%) and the second-highest ranked question was *How can AI systems remain robust and trustworthy amidst data shifts, performance decay, and misleading input?* which was ranked first by 24% (n=65) of the respondents. When comparing results across stakeholder groups, most stakeholders

ranked these two questions as the highest priority except for academia and healthcare professionals. This trend remains consistent when comparing rankings across levels of AI experience, except the small sample of individuals who have no AI experience display widely diverging preferences, while those who design or develop AI tools rank all questions nearly equally. Rankings for the remaining questions in this domain are shown in figure 2. Graphical results are available for all domains within supplementary material C.

Ranking of priorities for 'Accuracy and reliability of AI tools'

Priorities

- How can the accuracy and reliability of AI models be ensured when generating evidence and informing decisions, and how can limits be identified?
- How can AI systems stay robust and trustworthy amid data shifts, performance decay, and misleading inputs?
- When is explainability crucial in regulatory decisions, and what methods balance explainability with performance?
- How can consistency of AI performance be maintained across diverse datasets and clinical environments?

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Figure 2: Overall and stakeholder specific rankings of research questions within the domain

The top panel presents the distribution of respondent rankings (n=267) for the four research questions in this domain. Stacked horizontal bars display how each question was ranked by respondents with dark green representing top-ranked questions, followed by blue, yellow, and orange for progressively lower rankings. Higher ranks (first and second) are shown to the right of the vertical bar and lower ranks (third and fourth) to the left of the vertical bar. The lower panel displays a line graph (subway plot) illustrating how the different stakeholder groups (shown on the x axis) ranked the four research questions. The y axis shows the inverted mean rank within each stakeholder group, where lower mean indicating higher priority appear higher on the plot, while higher mean values, indicating lower ranks, appear lower. Each coloured line corresponds to one research question. Colours are aligned with the overall ranking among all respondents: green represents the question with the highest priority (lowest mean rank) within the domain, blue the second highest, yellow the third, and orange the fourth. Research questions have been abbreviated for all figures to enhance graphical clarity.

Accuracy and reliability of AI tools (n=267).

The second most prioritised domain was *Data governance, confidentiality, and consent* (figure 1). In this domain, the questions were more contested, with no definitive top-ranked question. The question *What models of informed consent are best when using health data for AI research beyond its original purpose?* received the highest ranking from the largest share of respondents (33%) (supplementary figure 6). There were no clear ranking patterns across stakeholder groups regarding the top-priority questions. When comparing rankings across levels of AI experience, the two highest-ranked questions tended to converge towards the mean among groups with at least some AI experience (supplementary figure 7). In contrast, the question concerning the best approach to the pseudonymisation/anonymisation for AI training was lowly ranked by groups actively involved in designing AI policies, while it was the top-ranked question among respondents with no AI experience (supplementary figure 8)

Ethics, fairness, and bias prevention domain was the third ranked domain overall. In this domain, all questions were ranked first by similar proportions of respondents (24%–27%). The question *What methods best spot and reduce the bias in AI models in medicine?* was ranked as the second highest priority by the largest share of respondents (supplementary figure 9). It was also the top-ranked question across all but one stakeholder group and across all but one level of AI experience, although often only by a small margin (supplementary figures 10-11).

The domain *Regulation and oversight* ranked fourth in the overall prioritisation of domains (figure 1). The rankings of research questions within this domain were very closely contested, with no clear top-ranked question. However, the question *What gaps exist in guidance for AI use in benefit-risk assessment, pharmacovigilance, and evidence generations?* received the largest proportion of first rankings (33%) (supplementary figure 12). When comparing results across stakeholder groups, a highly mixed pattern emerged, with no alignment in prioritisation (supplementary figure 13). Across levels of AI experience, the top three questions were prioritised similarly, with only minor variations between groups (supplementary figure 14).

The *Research integrity and intellectual property* domain ranked fifth in the overall prioritisation (figure 1). In this domain, two questions received similar rankings, and the question *How can transparency and reproducibility of results be strengthened in AI-enabled medicine development?* was most frequently ranked highest (supplementary figure 15). Across stakeholder groups, a mixed pattern was observed, although this top-prioritised question was consistently ranked highly in all stakeholder groups and in all groups with at least some AI experience (supplementary figures 16-17).

The *Resources and support for AI use* domain ranked sixth in the overall prioritisation (figure 1). Here, the question *Which technical checks and quality controls ensure AI systems are validated, secure, and reliable?* was the top ranked question by the largest proportion of respondents (43%) (supplementary figure 18). This question was also top ranked across all stakeholder groups and all AI experience groups (supplementary figures 19–20).

The domain *Impact on jobs and skills* was ranked lowest in overall priority overall (figure 1). Within this domain the question *What new skill sets will be important for future regulatory and medicine development*

work as AI expands? was ranked first by nearly half of the respondents (47%). (supplementary figure 21). This pattern was also observed across AI experience groups and stakeholder groups, with the exception of CROs, where this question was ranked third (supplementary figures 22-23).

Table 3 below displays the resulting number of research questions selected from each domain, informed by the weighting criteria.

Table 3: Number of questions selected from each domain

Domain name	Number of research questions selected
Accuracy & reliability of AI tools	3
Data governance, confidentiality, & consent	2
Ethics, fairness, & bias prevention	2
Regulation & oversight	1
Research integrity & intellectual property	1
Resources & support for AI use	1
Impact on jobs & skills	0

While the survey allowed for respondents to draft their own proposed research priorities, no specific clusters of suggestions were identified.

4. Discussion

This study provides a structured, multi-stakeholder assessment of priority research areas related to the use of AI across the medicines lifecycle. By design, the analysis focuses on perceived research needs rather than on the description of specific AI tools, applications, or regulatory activities. The discussion therefore interprets the findings as signals of where further regulatory science research may be required, rather than as recommendations for concrete regulatory actions.

Across all stakeholder groups, the domain *Accuracy and reliability of AI tools* emerged as the highest priority by a substantial margin. This finding suggests that stakeholders primarily associate the responsible use of AI in medicines development and evaluation with the ability to ensure robust performance, detect limitations, and manage uncertainty. Rather than questioning whether AI may be used, respondents appear most concerned with how AI-generated outputs can be trusted when they inform evidence generation and regulatory decision-making.

Closely following accuracy and reliability, the domains *Data governance, confidentiality, and consent* and *Ethics, fairness, and bias prevention* were prioritised by most respondents. Together, these results indicate that foundational conditions for trustworthy AI - data quality, lawful and ethical data use, and mitigation of bias - are perceived as the greatest pressing research challenges.

Importantly, the comparatively lower prioritisation of the domain *Regulation and oversight* should not be interpreted as a lack of concern for governance. Rather, it may reflect an implicit assumption among stakeholders that horizontal legal frameworks, including the EU Artificial Intelligence Act (17), already establish core requirements, shifting attention toward methodological questions that are not fully resolved by legislation alone.

Noticeably, within domains, the rankings of the four proposed questions were often only marginally different, indicating that respondents saw value across a broad range of challenges rather than converging on a single critical concern. This suggests a nuanced landscape of research needs, where multiple priorities coexist and often overlap across stakeholders.

After weighing the research challenges within each domain by overall domain priority, ten topics were identified as priority research areas:

1. How can the accuracy and reliability of AI models be ensured when they are used to generate clinical evidence and inform regulatory decisions, and how can limitations of AI for these purposes be identified? (*Accuracy and reliability*)
2. How can AI systems used in the medicines lifecycle and regulatory review remain robust and trustworthy when they face challenges like changing data, reduced performance over time, incomplete information, or misleading inputs? (*Accuracy and reliability*)

3. When is it important for AI models to be explainable in regulatory decision-making, and what methods best achieve that without affecting their performance? (*Accuracy and reliability*)
4. What models of informed consent or other legal basis are most appropriate when using health data for AI research beyond the original purpose the data were collected for? (*Data governance, confidentiality, and consent*)
5. How can data used in AI-based medicines development be made more secure and easier to audit or track? (*Data governance, confidentiality, and consent*)
6. What methods are most effective for spotting and reducing bias in AI models for use in medicines development and evaluation? (*Ethics, fairness, and bias prevention*)
7. What kind of transparency measures are necessary to clearly explain the limits and uncertainties of AI use in the medicines lifecycle? (*Ethics, fairness, and bias prevention*)
8. What gaps exist in current guidance for AI use in areas like benefit-risk assessment, monitoring medicine safety (pharmacovigilance), and clinical evidence generation? (*Regulation and oversight*)
9. How can transparency and reproducibility of results be strengthened in AI-enabled medicine development? (*Research integrity and intellectual property*)
10. Which technical checks and quality controls are essential to ensure that AI systems used in clinical trials, manufacturing, safety monitoring, and regulatory submissions are properly validated, secure, and reliable? (*Resources and support for AI use*)

This study has several limitations. Participation was uneven across stakeholder groups, with some groups underrepresented. The results therefore reflect the views of respondents who chose to participate and may not be fully generalisable. In addition, prioritisation was based on predefined domains and research questions, which may have constrained the range of issues considered

Furthermore, it cannot be ensured that the understanding of terms used in the questions is uniform across all groups that participated in the survey and all levels of experience of participants. While this pertains to all the addressed domains, it is specifically relevant for the *Accuracy and Reliability* domain

with technical terms in the description. Regarding the authors' definition and understanding of the terms "accuracy" and "reliability", accuracy is understood as referring to a result of performance assessment (how often a model is correct), while reliability includes considerations on dependability and trust, e.g. stability over time and consistence of results across environments and users (how consistent the model works). It is assumed that participants have a similar understanding.

Finally, the survey captures perceptions at a specific point in time; priorities may evolve as AI technologies, regulatory frameworks, and practical experience develop.

Despite these limitations, the study provides a structured overview of perceived regulatory research needs and highlights areas of convergence and divergence across stakeholders. While conducted in Europe, the results are considered to have global relevance.

Conclusion

The Network Data Steering Group consulted multiple stakeholders to identify their perceived regulatory science research priorities for AI in the medicines lifecycle. Accuracy and reliability emerged as the most important domain, contributing to three of the top ten priorities. While this work on stakeholders AI research priorities was conducted in the EU, we consider the results to be relevant to those working in medicines development and regulation around the world. These findings can guide future research by academic and regulatory science organizations, helping to strengthen the scientific foundation for the use of AI in medicines regulation.

5. Study Highlights

- What is the current knowledge on the topic?
 - Artificial intelligence is increasingly used across the medicines lifecycle, and regulators have articulated high-level principles for its trustworthy use, including requirements related to transparency, data governance, and ethics. The EU Artificial Intelligence Act establishes a horizontal legal framework for AI systems but does not define how AI-generated evidence should be evaluated in medicines regulation.
- What question did this study address?
 - This study identified and prioritised regulatory research needs related to the use of artificial intelligence in the medicines lifecycle, based on stakeholder perspectives across the European medicines regulatory network.
- What does this study add to our knowledge?
 - The study provides a network-wide, stakeholder-informed prioritisation of regulatory research areas for AI. It shows strong convergence on the importance of accuracy, reliability, data governance, and ethical considerations, while revealing heterogeneous expectations regarding regulation and oversight beyond existing legal frameworks.
- How might this change clinical pharmacology or translational science?
 - By clarifying priority areas for regulatory research, the findings support the development of scientific standards for assessing AI-enabled evidence in medicines development and evaluation, thereby strengthening regulatory decision-making and maintaining patient safety.

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7. Author Contributions statement

Wrote the manuscript: LP, AL, MO, JZ, KB, BH, SS, GW, K Broich, PA

Designed the research: LP, AL, MO, JZ, KB, BH, SS, GW, K Broich, PA

Performed the research: LP, AL, MO

Analysed the data: LP, AL, MO

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Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj/eng>

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material A: List of research questions and abbreviated questions

Domain	Question	Abbreviated question (where applicable)
Research integrity and IP	How can transparency and reproducibility of results be strengthened in AI-enabled medicine development?	How can transparency and reproducibility of results be strengthened in AI-enabled medicine development?
Research integrity and IP	What mechanisms can detect and prevent misuse or misrepresentation of AI models and their outputs?	What mechanisms can detect and prevent misuse or misrepresentation of AI models and their outputs?
Research integrity and IP	What approaches can promote accountability for responsible review of AI-generated outputs in the context of medicine development and evaluation?	What approaches can promote accountability in reviewing AI-generated outputs in medicine development?
Research integrity and IP	What frameworks or standards best ensure proper attribution and credit for datasets, models, and algorithms in AI research?	What frameworks or standards ensure proper attribution for datasets, models, and algorithms in AI research?
Accuracy and reliability of AI tools	How can the accuracy and reliability of AI models be ensured when they are used to generate clinical evidence and inform regulatory decisions, and how can	How can the accuracy and reliability of AI models be ensured when generating evidence and informing decisions, and how can limits be identified?

Domain	Question	Abbreviated question (where applicable)
	<p>limitations of AI for these purposes be identified?</p>	
<p>Accuracy and reliability of AI tools</p>	<p>How can AI systems used in the medicines lifecycle and regulatory review remain robust and trustworthy when they face challenges like changing data, reduced performance over time, incomplete information, or misleading inputs?</p>	<p>How can AI systems stay robust and trustworthy amid data shifts, performance decay, and misleading inputs?</p>
<p>Accuracy and reliability of AI tools</p>	<p>How can consistency of AI performance be maintained across diverse datasets and clinical environments?</p>	<p>How can consistency of AI performance be maintained across diverse datasets and clinical environments?</p>
<p>Accuracy and reliability of AI tools</p>	<p>When is it important for AI models to be explainable (transparent reasoning) in regulatory decision-making, and what methods best achieve that without affecting their performance?</p>	<p>When is explainability crucial in regulatory decisions, and what methods balance explainability with performance?</p>
<p>Data governance, confidentiality, and consent</p>	<p>What are the most effective ways to anonymise/pseudonymise data while still keeping it useful for AI training?</p>	<p>What are the best ways to anonymise/pseudonymise data while still keeping it useful for AI training?</p>

Domain	Question	Abbreviated question (where applicable)
Data governance, confidentiality, and consent	What standards or processes are needed to develop and maintain benchmarking datasets for AI in medicines development and evaluation?	What standards or processes are needed to develop and maintain benchmarking datasets for AI?
Data governance, confidentiality, and consent	How can data used in AI-based medicine development be made more secure and easier to audit or track?	How can data used in AI-based medicine development be made more secure and easier to audit or track?
Data governance, confidentiality, and consent	What models of informed consent or other legal basis are most appropriate when using health data for AI research beyond the original purpose the data were collected for?	What models of informed consent are best when using health data for AI research beyond its original purpose?
Regulation and oversight	What methodologies can be used to assess whether existing regulatory guidance remains relevant and robust in the face of evolving AI technologies in medicines development?	What methodologies can assess if current guidance remains relevant and robust as AI evolves?
Regulation and oversight	What gaps exist in current guidance for AI use in areas like benefit-risk assessment, monitoring medicine safety	What gaps exist in guidance for AI use in benefit-risk assessment, pharmacovigilance, and evidence generation?

Domain	Question	Abbreviated question (where applicable)
	(pharmacovigilance), and clinical evidence generation?	
Regulation and oversight	How can international regulatory alignment for AI in medicines development be facilitated?	How can international regulatory alignment for AI in medicines development be facilitated?
Regulation and oversight	How can clear definitions of roles and responsibilities be developed on the use of AI in regulatory submissions?	How can clear definitions of roles and responsibilities be developed on the use of AI in regulatory submissions?
Ethics, fairness, and bias prevention	What is the right way to set up independent ethical oversight for how AI is used in medicine development and evaluation?	How should independent ethical oversight for AI in medicine development be set up?
Ethics, fairness, and bias prevention	What methods are most effective for spotting and reducing bias in AI models for use in medicines development and evaluation?	What methods best spot and reduce bias in AI models in medicine?
Ethics, fairness, and bias prevention	What kind of transparency measures are necessary to clearly explain the limits and uncertainties of AI use in the medicines lifecycle?	What transparency measures clearly explain the limits and uncertainties of AI use in medicine?
Ethics, fairness, and bias prevention	How can it be ensured that data used to train AI is diverse enough to help reduce health inequalities?	How can it be ensured that data used to train AI is diverse enough to help reduce health inequalities?

Domain	Question	Abbreviated question (where applicable)
Resources and support for AI use	How should AI suppliers, cloud providers, and data partners be qualified and monitored to meet EU quality and regulatory standard expectations?	How should AI suppliers and other partners be qualified and monitored to meet EU standards?
Resources and support for AI use	How can AI systems be designed and deployed in ways that minimise environmental impact, including energy use and data storage?	How can AI systems be designed and deployed to minimize environmental impact?
Resources and support for AI use	What resources and collaboration mechanisms (e.g., shared reference/benchmark datasets, networks like DARWIN EU®) are needed to support independent testing and ongoing monitoring of AI used in medicines development and evaluation?	What resources and collaboration mechanisms support independent testing and monitoring of AI?
Resources and support for AI use	Which technical checks and quality controls are essential to ensure that AI systems used in clinical trials, manufacturing, safety monitoring, and regulatory submissions are properly validated, secure, and reliable?	Which technical checks and quality controls ensure AI systems are validated, secure, and reliable?

Domain	Question	Abbreviated question (where applicable)
Impact on jobs and skills	What strategies can reduce negative workforce impacts while still making the most of AI benefits?	What strategies can reduce negative workforce impacts while still making the most of AI benefits?
Impact on jobs and skills	Which roles in medicine development and evaluation are most affected by AI adoption?	Which roles in medicine development and evaluation are most affected by AI adoption?
Impact on jobs and skills	How can change management strategies support adoption of AI in healthcare systems?	How can change management strategies support adoption of AI in healthcare systems?
Impact on jobs and skills	What new skill sets will be important for future work in regulatory and medicines development as AI becomes more common?	What new skill sets will be important for future regulatory and medicine development work as AI expands?

Supplementary material B: Selection of responses to open-ended questions

Forty-two respondents provided a response to at least one open-ended question. Most responses reiterated the importance of a particular research question proposed in the survey, justified their ranking, or stated that each question was important. Additional themes and quotations are provided below.

Recurring cross-cutting themes

- Several respondents highlighted the need for equitable access to training data, resources, infrastructure, etc. for smaller enterprises to compete
- Multiple respondents indicated that the research questions were hard to prioritise with them all being important.

Accuracy and reliability of AI tools

Select quotes:

“Inaccurate tools can directly harm patients or delay diagnosis, so reliability is non-negotiable.” – Patient/consumer

“Ultimately, the value of AI-enabled technologies in practice is directly related to their performance, and our ability to identify performance degradation. Without the means to assure suitable monitoring of performance, risk is increased in ways that are difficult to predict and manage.” — Contract research organisation member

Data governance, confidentiality, and consent

Recurring themes:

- Existing regulations, such as GDPR and AU Act, were referenced along with calls for clearer interpretation and harmonisation across Member States.
- Withdrawal of consent is a critical challenge in this domain.

Select quotes:

“Companies are already experienced in anonymizing and pseudonymizing data, perhaps a better question is ‘Does the scale of AI impact how data is anonymized/pseudonymized?’” —

Industry member

“Patients should maintain a level of control over [their data] for care or innovation purposes. For example, the opt-out mechanism introduced in the EHDS can enable this control but only if it is well implemented...” — Healthcare professional

“...It would be very beneficial to identify opportunities to look for a clear conflict mechanism... and strive for the creation of more legal grounds for data processing of personal data in the EU AIA and Data Act... We also highlight the remaining ambiguity created by the GDPR, and challenges around withdrawal of consent when patient data has been used to train an AI model.” — Industry member

Ethics, fairness, and bias prevention

Select quotes:

“Understanding the way AI handles edge cases is closely aligned to setting appropriate limits on trusted application.” — Contract research organisation member

“AI can unintentionally reproduce or amplify existing inequalities. Ethical design and diverse datasets are crucial to avoid bias and guarantee that all patient groups—including under-represented populations—benefit equally.” — Patient/consumer

Regulation and oversight

Recurring theme:

- Industry members requested clarity on research and development exemptions in the AI Act.
- Respondents indicated a need for harmonised guidance and legislation.

Select quotes:

“Create a risk-based tiered system which outlines areas where AI is and can start being implemented now... and areas where more validation/confidence is needed.” – Patient/consumer

“Facilitating international regulatory alignment on AI is essential... while fostering innovation, accelerating global drug development, and building trust in AI-driven decision-making.” – Industry member

Research integrity and intellectual property

Select quotes:

“Patients must know that their data and biological information are used responsibly and with clear ownership principles.” – Patient/consumer

“To realize this potential... the framework must balance data sharing with robust protection for trade secrets.” – Industry member

Resources and support for AI use

Select quotes:

“Ensuring robust resources and support for AI use is important because it directly impacts the equitable access to AI technologies... Without adequate funding, infrastructure, and tools, only well-resourced organisations or regions may benefit.” — Industry member

“Data access is the most critical aspect.” — Industry member

“Hard to prioritise – all very important.” — National competent authority member

Impact on jobs and skills

Select quotes:

“Work in this area should be holistic [for example] also thinking about what skills should be taught during education at all levels and the more general education/awareness that will be required across all parts of society.” — Industry member

"I consider this domain less critical compared to others, as the primary focus in AI for medicine should be on ensuring safety, accuracy, and ethical use rather than workforce transitions." —

Patient/consumer

Supplementary material C: Research question rankings by overall, stakeholder group, and level of AI experience

1. Accuracy and reliability of AI tools

Figure 3. Accuracy and reliability of AI tools average question rankings

Ranking of priorities for 'Accuracy and reliability of AI tools'

How can the accuracy and reliability of AI models be ensured when generating evidence and informing decisions, and how can limits be identified?

How can AI systems stay robust and trustworthy amid data shifts, performance decay, and misleading inputs?

When is explainability crucial in regulatory decisions, and what methods balance explainability with performance?

How can consistency of AI performance be maintained across diverse datasets and clinical environments?

n = 267 respondents

Figure 4. Accuracy and reliability of AI tools question rankings by stakeholder

Figure 5. Accuracy and reliability of AI tools question rankings by AI experience

2. Data governance, confidentiality, and consent

Figure 6. Data governance, confidentiality, and consent average question rankings

Ranking of priorities for 'Data governance, confidentiality and consent'

Figure 7. Data governance, confidentiality, and consent question rankings by stakeholder

Figure 8. Data governance, confidentiality, and consent question rankings by AI experience

3. Ethics, fairness, and bias prevention

Figure 9. Ethics, fairness, and bias prevention average question rankings

Ranking of priorities for 'Ethics, fairness and bias prevention'

Figure 10. Ethics, fairness, and bias prevention question rankings by stakeholder

Figure 11. Ethics, fairness, and bias prevention question rankings by AI experience

4. Regulation and oversight

Figure 12. Regulation and oversight average question rankings

Ranking of priorities for 'Regulation and oversight'

What gaps exist in guidance for AI use in benefit-risk assessment, pharmacovigilance, and evidence generation?

What methodologies can assess if current guidance remains relevant and robust as AI evolves?

How can international regulatory alignment for AI in medicines development be facilitated?

How can clear definitions of roles and responsibilities be developed on the use of AI in regulatory submissions?

Rank 1st 2nd 3rd 4th

n = 262 respondents

Figure 13. Regulation and oversight question rankings by stakeholder

Figure 14. Regulation and oversight question rankings by AI experience

5. Research integrity and intellectual property

Figure 15. Research integrity and intellectual property average question rankings

Ranking of priorities for 'Research integrity and intellectual property'

What mechanisms can detect and prevent misuse or misrepresentation of AI models and their outputs?

How can transparency and reproducibility of results be strengthened in AI-enabled medicine development?

What approaches can promote accountability in reviewing AI-generated outputs in medicine development?

What frameworks or standards ensure proper attribution for datasets, models, and algorithms in AI research?

Rank 1st 2nd 3rd 4th

n = 256 respondents

Figure 16. Research integrity and intellectual property question rankings by stakeholder

Figure 17. Research integrity and intellectual property question rankings by AI experience

6. Resources and support for AI use

Figure 18. Resources and support for AI use average question rankings

Ranking of priorities for 'Resources and support for AI use'

Figure 19. Resources and support for AI use question rankings by stakeholder

Figure 20. Resources and support for AI use question rankings by AI experience

7. Impact on jobs and skills

Figure 21. Impact on jobs and skills average question rankings

Ranking of priorities for 'Impact on jobs and skills'

Figure 22. Impact on jobs and skills question rankings by stakeholder

Figure 23. Impact on jobs and skills question rankings by AI experience

